

Redefining Processing Efficiency with In-Memory Computing Architecture

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ABSTRACT

In-memory computing offers a transformative solution to address the bottlenecks of conventional computing architectures, where frequent data transfer between memory and processors limits performance. This study presents the design and evaluation of an in-memory computing architecture aimed at significantly reducing latency, enhancing energy efficiency, and increasing throughput by performing computations directly within memory arrays. By embedding logic functions alongside memory components, the proposed architecture achieves notable improvements in computational efficiency. Experimental results reveal that the architecture reduces latency by up to 43.33%, with tasks such as matrix multiplication demonstrating a decrease from 450 microseconds to 275 microseconds. Energy consumption is reduced by over 40%, as evidenced by neural network inference requiring only 7.2 joules compared to 12.5 joules in baseline systems. Furthermore, the architecture enhances throughput by up to 52%, with AI model training achieving 1,520,000 operations per second compared to 1,000,000 in traditional architectures. These results establish the potential of in-memory computing to redefine conventional processing paradigms, delivering high-speed, energy-efficient computations for applications in AI, machine learning, and other data-intensive domains.

Keywords: In-Memory Computing, Latency Reduction, Energy-Efficient Architecture, Data-Intensive Processing, Memory-Integrated Logic, AI Acceleration

INTRODUCTION

The explosive growth of data-based applications, including Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), Big-Data analytics, and Real-Time systems, has heightened the demand for computing systems capable of handling extremely large amounts of data efficiently [1]. However, conventional von Neumann architectures, where computation and memory functions are physically detached, will inevitably be increasingly unable to meet these real-time requirements, mainly due to inefficiencies introduced by frequent data movement between memory and processors [2]. This architectural separation is not only tremendously latency-prone, but it also incurs up to 1000 times more energy consumption due to the frequent movement of data between memory and processors, which bottlenecks the performance and scalability of modern computing systems [3]. Dynamic Random Access Memory (DRAM), a fundamental technology of main memory, has been playing a significant role in overall system performance. However, DRAM-based memory subsystems have been struggling to meet the growing requirements of modern workloads [4]. The problems of bandwidth saturation, limited capacity, and rapidly rising energy consumption have been rendering memory itself the most critical bottleneck for high-performance computing. These problems are not lessened by the diminishing pace of technology scaling, as it becomes increasingly difficult for DRAM cells to retain their stability in terms of reliability, capacity, and efficiency [5].

The cost of data movement in traditional architectures has compounded these challenges. Each time a data operation is performed, fetching happens in memory, transporting data itself to the processor, and performing computation, thereafter, writing data back into memory. This constant shuttling of data involves great latency while a disproportionate amount of energy exists to be consumed by crossing this huge distance compared to simple arithmetic performed locally. The consequent inefficiency, which is also popularly referred to as the "memory wall," has become an insurmountable hurdle to efficiently further enhance the computational speed of completing any task at hand [6]. As applications become increasingly data-centric, with larger datasets and real-time processing

requirements, the limitations of processor-centric architectures have become glaringly apparent. Traditional approaches to improving performance—such as adding more cores or increasing clock speeds—are no longer sufficient to address the growing gap between computation and memory capabilities. The need for architectural innovation has never been more critical. In-memory computing (IMC) offers a transformative approach to overcoming these challenges [6-7]. By embedding computational capabilities directly within memory arrays, IMC eliminates the need for excessive data movement, thereby reducing latency and energy consumption. This paradigm shift not only addresses the memory wall problem but also enables new opportunities for accelerating data-intensive tasks by leveraging the inherent parallelism of memory architectures.

Recent advances in memory technologies have made IMC increasingly viable. Innovations such as 3D-stacked DRAM and emerging non-volatile memory (NVM) technologies enable the integration of logic and memory on the same chip, paving the way for practical implementations of IMC [8]. These advancements allow for efficient execution of operations directly within memory, such as bulk data manipulation, matrix multiplications, and search functions, which are critical for workloads like AI and ML. IMC architectures challenge the traditional dominance of the central processing unit (CPU) in computing systems. By decentralizing computation and empowering memory subsystems to handle a share of the processing load, IMC redefines the relationship between processing and storage elements. This shift aligns with the growing demand for architectures that are not only high-performing but also energy-efficient and sustainable [9]. With increasing focus on the data and with exponential datasets and real-time processing needs, the deficiencies of processor-centric architectures are glaring. Few-cheered performances—from revived concurrent computation or higher clock frequency scaling—just cannot slay the widening divide between computation and memory performance. Architectural innovations need to fill this gap to unlock future designs. In-memory computing (IMC) is a major step toward solving these challenges [8]. IMC embeds processing capabilities within memory arrays, preserving innovation, reducing latency and saving power by completely shaving off deadly data movements. Besides addressing the memory wall issue, the changes provide a wider avenue of opportunities for exploiting parallelism in memory architectures for speeding up data-heavy tasks [10]. Recent developments in memory technologies have paved the way for IMC to become more practical. 3D-stacked DRAM and other, newly developed non-volatile memory (NVM) technologies open the way to integrating logic and memory into the same chip, thus realizing IMC implementations [8-9]. The advances let such array operations, for instance, bulk data manipulation, multiplication of matrices, and searching algorithms necessary in many operations such as AI and ML, get implemented.

The IMC technologies comparatively question the established centrality of GPU computing systems. With its spread of computational capabilities across the memory subsystems, IMC paves a way to break the silicon dichotomy between processing and storage elements. It corresponds to the changing demand for architectures that both high-performing as well as sustainably energy-efficient. The benefits of IMC are far reaching beyond performance gains. The reduction of data movement calls for energy-efficient architectures, considered practical for power-constrained applications, especially edge computing devices and mobile platforms, where energy constraints often limit the capabilities of the architecture [11]. These motivate IMC to offer a new perspective toward system-level optimization [12]. Through the embedding of processing inside memory, designers can look toward new approaches on workload partitioning, scheduling, and resource allocation that would take advantage of IMC's special capabilities. This holistic view has the potential to unleash unprecedented efficiency and performance. The intent of this work is to investigate the design and implementation of IMC architectures that provide solutions to the burdens and limitations of traditional systems. By using recent improvements in memory technologies and computational paradigms, this proposed architecture shows how IMC lays down a new face of processing efficiency for contemporary workloads. Together with experimental evidence to support the findings, an exploration is provided showing the true promise of IMC work and the scope of its applications, advantages, and challenges. Hence, this work contributes to the body of IMC knowledge whereby the groundwork is prepared for more explorations and breakthroughs within this promising field. The outcomes in this paper demonstrate the pivotal need for a novel paradigm to reduce traditional thinking in computing and recognize that memory-centric architectures may lock the future for high-performance computing.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of in-memory computing (IMC) has its origins in the anticipatory efforts towards enhancing the inefficiencies of von Neumann architectures, wherein the physical separation of memory and processing long ago was recognized as an inherent limitation [2-4, 6]. Early inspirations of near-data processing (NDP) exposed the relevancy of how to slash data movement to better performance and energy consumption, especially with data-intensive workloads [13]. Thus, early efforts formed the basis from which IMC could develop as signifying an architectural paradigm [6]. One of the eldest IMC implementations involves performing bulk operations within DRAM, such as row copy and bitwise operations. These techniques capitalized on the already-established structure of DRAM for conducting simple computations within the arrays of memory themselves, thus displaying the promise of dramatically reducing data movement [4, 14]. Although manifestly limited, these early works offered

quite some advice on the importance and hence the initial values of integrating computation into memory. The appearance of 3D-stacked memory technologies waxed a big opportunity for IMC, with architectures like Hybrid Memory Cube (HMC) and High-Bandwidth Memory (HBM) gaining the capability of inserting logic layers inside memory stacks, providing sufficient high internal bandwidth to ensure efficient in-memory computations and opening venues for embedding more complex logic functions within memory modules [15-16].

Research into IMC has since branched into a plethora of application domains, from artificial intelligence and machine learning to database processing and graph analytics. These application domains are ideal candidates for IMC given their large datasets and operations that are amenable to parallelization. For instance, IMC permits orders-of-magnitude accelerations over traditional architectures for fundamental machine learning operations like matrix multiplications [11, 17]. Data from experimental implementations of IMC have illustrated the possibility of large performance and energy efficiency gains for certain workloads. For instance, IMC-based accelerators have shown promise in applications ranging from natural language processing to image recognition. These achievements lay bare the change-inducing potential for IMC to reshape the performance envelope of modern computing systems [11]. Regardless of the promise any IMC may have, it is laden with common caveats and challenges it will face in its maturation process. One of the first is the general design of efficient in-memory logic arrays that would appeal to existing memory technologies. Ordinary memory fabrication processes are suboptimal for logic design and demand fresh accommodation for compatibility and performance. Another major concern is thermal management in IMC systems. The inclusion of computing elements in the memory arrays leads to extremely high-power density that may even cause overheating; consequently, reliability becomes a major concern. To this end, the design of IMC architecture will need to consider thermal constraints, and a proper heat dissipation mechanism must be designed. However, to see IMC's widespread acceptance, one needs a systemic viewpoint to deal with the technical, economic, and ecosystem issues. Moreover, close cooperation between academia, industry, and, on this road, standards organizations turn into one of the fundamental building blocks essential for the development and standardization of technologies-based IMC while maintaining coherence with current systems of operation. Overall, the presented literature review highlights the progress made in IMC research while identifying the challenges that remain.

METHODOLOGY

This study focuses on the design, implementation, and evaluation of an innovative in-memory computing (IMC) architecture aimed at redefining processing efficiency by minimizing data movement between memory and computational units. The methodology comprises four key stages: architecture design, logic embedding, hardware simulation, and performance evaluation. Each stage is carefully tailored to address the specific challenges of latency reduction, energy efficiency, and throughput enhancement.

Architecture Design: The proposed in-memory computing architecture integrates computational capabilities directly into memory cells, leveraging resistive memory elements such as SRAM and DRAM. The design incorporates a hybrid computational model where memory arrays perform both storage and fundamental logic operations (e.g., addition, multiplication) using minimal external processor intervention. Key design elements include: *Row-Parallel Computation:* Performing logic operations across memory rows simultaneously to exploit high parallelism. *Bitline Manipulation:* Encoding computational instructions through voltage levels applied to bitlines, enabling logical operations like AND, OR, and XOR directly in memory. The mathematical basis for in-memory operations is expressed as follows:

Basic Logic Operations:

- AND: $A \cdot B$, where A and B represent binary values stored in adjacent memory cells.
- OR: $A + B - (A \cdot B)$
- XOR: $A \oplus B = (A + B) - 2 \cdot (A \cdot B)$

Arithmetic Operations: Additions are realized through cascading XOR gates, while multiplication is implemented using partial product generation and accumulation within memory blocks.

Logic Embedding in Memory Arrays: To implement computations directly within memory arrays, a systematic embedding of logic gates within standard memory architecture is performed. This involves: *Gate-Level Integration:* Embedding logic gates such as XOR and AND directly into memory row decoders. *Mapping Computational Tasks:* Translating data-intensive tasks into memory-accessible formats where computation occurs without external data transfer.

The embedded logic design leverages the following matrix-based operational framework for memory computations:

$$R = M \cdot W + B$$

Where, R is the result matrix, M is the input data matrix, W is the weight matrix, and B is the bias vector, commonly applied in AI workloads.

Hardware Simulation: The proposed architecture is simulated using a combination of circuit-level and system-level tools. The simulation workflow involves: *Circuit-Level Validation:* Employing SPICE simulations to validate the

functionality of in-memory operations at the transistor level, ensuring logical correctness and stability. *System-Level Modeling*: Using tools such as GEM5 or NVSim for evaluating overall performance, latency, and energy consumption under various workloads.

Performance Evaluation: The evaluation framework compares the proposed architecture with conventional von Neumann-based systems across the following parameters:

Latency: Measured as the time taken to complete computational tasks, with metrics derived using the formula:

$$\text{Latency Improvement} = \frac{\text{Baseline Latency} - \text{Proposed Latency}}{\text{Baseline Latency}} \times 100\%$$

Energy Efficiency: Calculated based on power consumption per computational cycle:

$$\text{Energy Efficiency} = \frac{\text{Baseline Energy Consumption}}{\text{Proposed Energy Consumption}} \times 100\%$$

Defined as the number of operations per second, particularly for AI and machine learning benchmarks.

Experimental Workflow: Synthetic Workloads: Simulations using synthetic datasets to assess baseline performance. Real-World Applications: Applying the architecture to machine learning models such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for benchmarking. Comparative Analysis: Performance metrics are compared against existing architectures, emphasizing reductions in latency and energy consumption.

The experimental results demonstrate a significant improvement in computational throughput, with energy savings of up to 40% compared to traditional architectures. The findings underscore the potential of in-memory computing to revolutionize processing paradigms, particularly for data-intensive tasks in AI and beyond.

Figure 1: Architecture Flowchart of the Proposed In-Memory Computing Design for Enhanced Processing Efficiency

These steps collectively enable the proposed in-memory computing architecture to achieve high-speed, energy-efficient processing while addressing the challenges of data transfer and computational latency in conventional systems. The architecture flowchart for the proposed in-memory computing system outlines the sequential and integrated processes that redefine computational efficiency by embedding logic functions directly into memory arrays. The architecture begins with the Input Data Mapping Module, where input data is formed into a memory-compatible structure, ensuring that data streams are aligned with the memory architecture's operational requirements. This module is crucial for converting raw data into bit-level representations suitable for in-memory processing. Next, the Logic Integration and Data Storage Unit manages the dual functionality of memory arrays, embedding logic gates such as XOR, AND, and OR within the memory cells. Here, the data is both stored and processed, with computational operations being executed in parallel across memory rows to achieve high throughput. This unit incorporates voltage-based manipulation of bitlines to execute logical and arithmetic operations efficiently.

The processed data is then fed into the Result Aggregation and Control Block, which consolidates intermediate results and ensures synchronization across memory arrays. This block employs accumulation techniques for

complex operations like matrix multiplication, crucial for tasks such as AI and machine learning computations. Finally, the Output Interface Module translates processed memory data back into application-specific results, providing compatibility with external systems. This module ensures seamless integration of the in-memory computing system with broader computational pipelines, delivering processed outputs with minimal latency. The architecture is supported by Performance Monitoring Units, strategically placed to evaluate key metrics such as energy consumption, latency, and throughput during operations. These units provide real-time feedback for further optimization of the system. This architecture flowchart emphasizes the modular design and seamless data flow that enables high-speed, energy-efficient computation directly within memory arrays.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed in-memory computing (IMC) architecture was evaluated across various parameters, including latency, energy efficiency, and throughput. These metrics were assessed using synthetic and real-world workloads, with a particular focus on data-intensive applications like AI and machine learning. Below are the results in tabular format, providing a comprehensive comparison with conventional von Neumann architectures. The experimental evaluation demonstrates significant improvements in processing efficiency, energy savings, and computational throughput. The following tables outline the key results, illustrating the proposed architecture's performance against conventional systems. Each table highlights specific aspects of the architecture's capabilities, showcasing its potential to address bottlenecks in traditional computing frameworks.

The results presented in Table 1 and illustrated in Figure 2 provide a comparative analysis of latency between the baseline von Neumann architecture and the proposed in-memory computing (IMC) architecture. The table and figure underscore the significant latency reductions achieved by the IMC design across various data-intensive tasks, demonstrating its capability to address the inherent bottlenecks of traditional computing systems. For matrix multiplication, a computationally intensive task frequently used in machine learning and AI applications, the proposed architecture reduced latency from 450 microseconds in the baseline system to 275 microseconds, yielding an improvement of 38.89%. This improvement is attributed to the elimination of repetitive data transfers between memory and processors, as the computations are performed directly within the memory arrays. In the case of convolution operations, which are fundamental to neural network processing, the IMC architecture demonstrated a reduction in latency from 320 microseconds to 185 microseconds, achieving an improvement of 42.19%. The ability to execute logical operations directly in the memory cells greatly enhances the parallelism, accelerating such workloads.

Figure 2: Latency Performance Comparison of Baseline and In-Memory Computing Architectures

For data sorting, a common operation in data analytics, the latency dropped from 150 microseconds to 85 microseconds, with an improvement of 43.33%. This substantial gain is due to the reduced need for iterative data movement, which often slows down sorting algorithms in conventional architectures. Overall, the results illustrate that the proposed IMC architecture achieves up to 43% latency reduction across diverse applications. These findings validate the design's effectiveness in minimizing processing delays by embedding computation within memory structures. The improvements highlighted in Table 1 and depicted in Figure 2 confirm that this approach offers a transformative solution for enhancing performance in data-intensive domains, paving the way for faster and more efficient computing systems. The in-memory computing architecture achieved up to 43% reduction in latency by eliminating the data transfer bottlenecks inherent in conventional architectures.

Table 1: Latency Comparison (in Microseconds)

Application	Baseline Architecture	Proposed IMC Architecture	Improvement (%)
Matrix Multiplication	450	275	38.89
Convolution Operations	320	185	42.19
Data Sorting	150	85	43.33

Figure 3: Energy Consumption Comparison Between Baseline and In-Memory Computing Architectures

The results outlined in Table 2 and visualized in Figure 3 highlight the significant reductions in energy consumption achieved by the proposed in-memory computing (IMC) architecture compared to traditional baseline architectures. These reductions underscore the energy efficiency of performing computations directly within memory arrays, a key advantage of the IMC approach. For neural network inference, a process that requires intensive matrix computations and repeated data access, the baseline system consumed 12.5 joules, whereas the IMC architecture

required only 7.2 joules. This 42.4% energy savings stems from the elimination of frequent data transfers between the memory and processor, which are a primary source of energy inefficiency in conventional systems. In the case of large-scale data search, where the rapid processing of vast datasets is critical, the energy consumption dropped from 8.7 joules to 5.1 joules, resulting in a 41.38% improvement. The IMC architecture’s ability to execute logical operations within memory arrays reduces the energy overhead associated with moving data across the processing pipeline, thus achieving considerable savings.

Table 2: Energy Consumption Comparison (in Joules)

Application	Baseline Architecture	Proposed IMC Architecture	Energy Savings (%)
Neural Network Inference	12.5	7.2	42.4
Large-Scale Data Search	8.7	5.1	41.38
Sorting Operations	4.5	2.7	40.00

For sorting operations, a foundational task in data analytics, the energy consumption decreased from 4.5 joules to 2.7 joules, providing a 40.00% reduction. This improvement highlights the energy-efficient execution of iterative computations within memory, which minimizes the power required for external data handling. Overall, the results demonstrate that the IMC architecture consistently reduces energy consumption by over 40% across diverse applications. This makes the architecture particularly well-suited for energy-constrained environments, such as portable devices and edge computing systems. Figure 3 visually reinforces these findings, showing the substantial energy savings achieved across all evaluated tasks, validating the IMC design as a transformative solution for enhancing energy efficiency in data-intensive processing. The proposed design reduced energy consumption by over 40% for data-intensive tasks, highlighting its suitability for energy-constrained applications.

Figure 4: Throughput Performance Comparison Between Baseline and In-Memory Computing Architectures

The results presented in Table 3 and illustrated in Figure 4 showcase the significant throughput gains achieved by the proposed in-memory computing (IMC) architecture compared to the baseline architecture. Throughput, measured as operations per second, highlights the architecture's ability to handle computationally demanding tasks efficiently and at a scale. For AI model training, a resource-intensive process requiring extensive matrix multiplications and parameter updates, the baseline system achieved a throughput of 1,000,000 operations per second. In contrast, the IMC architecture increased this performance to 1,520,000 operations per second, representing a substantial 52.0% improvement. This boost in throughput is attributed to the IMC's parallel processing capabilities, which execute computations directly within the memory arrays, reducing overheads associated with data movement. In real-time data processing, which demands rapid handling and analysis of incoming data streams, the IMC architecture demonstrated a throughput gain from 800,000 operations per second in the baseline architecture to 1,210,000 operations per second, an improvement of 51.25%. The enhanced parallelism and minimized latency of the IMC design enable it to process real-time workloads more effectively, making it ideal for applications requiring immediate responses, such as edge computing and IoT. For image classification, a critical component of computer vision systems, the IMC architecture achieved a throughput of 1,780,000 operations per

second, compared to 1,200,000 operations per second with the baseline architecture, reflecting an improvement of 48.33%. This gain underscores the architecture's ability to handle large-scale image datasets and perform computationally intensive tasks with reduced delays. The results emphasize the transformative impact of the IMC architecture, with throughput improvements of up to 52% across diverse tasks. Figure 4 visually reinforces these findings, illustrating the consistent gains achieved by the IMC design. These improvements validate the architecture's potential for applications requiring high-speed processing, particularly in AI, big data, and real-time analytics. The integration of computational logic directly into memory not only enhances speed but also establishes the IMC approach as a robust solution for accelerating data-intensive workloads. Throughput improvements of up to 52% were observed, underscoring the architecture's ability to handle computationally demanding tasks with enhanced speed.

Table 3: Throughput Comparison (Operations per Second)

Task	Baseline Architecture	Proposed IMC Architecture	Throughput Gain (%)
AI Model Training	1,000,000	1,520,000	52.0
Real-Time Data Processing	800,000	1,210,000	51.25
Image Classification	1,200,000	1,780,000	48.33

The results of this study demonstrate the transformative potential of in-memory computing (IMC) architectures in addressing the limitations of conventional von Neumann-based systems. By integrating computational logic directly into memory arrays, the proposed IMC design successfully reduces latency, enhances energy efficiency, and increases throughput, as evidenced by the results across diverse computational tasks. The IMC architecture showed a significant reduction in latency, with improvements reaching up to 43%. This reduction is primarily due to the elimination of the frequent data transfers between memory and the processor, which are inherent bottlenecks in conventional architectures. For computationally intensive tasks such as matrix multiplication and convolution operations, these improvements underscore the architecture's ability to handle workloads efficiently by performing computations directly within the memory framework. These findings highlight the IMC architecture as a promising solution for latency-sensitive applications like AI and machine learning. Energy consumption results further validate the efficiency of the IMC design, with over 40% energy savings observed across all evaluated tasks. The reduction is attributed to the streamlined execution of operations within memory arrays, which minimizes the power-intensive process of data movement. The energy efficiency of the IMC design makes it particularly suitable for energy-constrained environments such as portable devices, IoT systems, and edge computing platforms. These results indicate that the architecture can significantly contribute to reducing the overall energy footprint of data-intensive applications, addressing a critical challenge in modern computing. The IMC architecture exhibited throughput improvements of up to 52%, demonstrating its ability to accelerate computationally demanding workloads. The enhanced parallelism achieved by performing operations directly in memory arrays enables the architecture to handle large-scale tasks such as AI model training, real-time data processing, and image classification with remarkable efficiency. These improvements establish the IMC architecture as a highly effective solution for applications requiring high-speed processing and scalability.

The consistent performance improvements across all metrics—latency, energy consumption, and throughput—highlight the versatility and robustness of the IMC architecture. The design addresses critical challenges in traditional computing systems, paving the way for broader adoption in domains where high performance and energy efficiency are paramount. Moreover, the architecture's suitability for AI and machine learning tasks positions it as a key enabler for advancements in these fields, particularly for applications that require processing large datasets with minimal delays. While the results are promising, further work is required to evaluate the scalability of the IMC architecture in more complex systems with diverse workloads. Integration challenges, such as compatibility with existing computing frameworks and addressing potential memory wear-out issues, also require attention. Future research could explore hybrid approaches that combine IMC with other emerging architectures to maximize performance while ensuring long-term reliability. In this proposed IMC architecture demonstrates a paradigm shift in computing by redefining efficiency and performance in data-intensive applications. The results establish a strong foundation for further exploration of in-memory computing as a transformative technology for next-generation systems.

CONCLUSION

This study has demonstrated the potential of in-memory computing (IMC) architectures to overcome the critical bottlenecks of conventional von Neumann architectures by embedding computational logic directly within memory arrays. The evaluation results, presented across latency, energy consumption, and throughput metrics, highlight the architecture's effectiveness in enhancing computational efficiency for data-intensive tasks. The proposed IMC design achieved a 43.33% reduction in latency for tasks such as data sorting, where latency decreased from 150 microseconds to 85 microseconds. Similarly, for convolution operations, a core component in AI and machine

learning workloads, the latency improvement reached 42.19%, demonstrating the architecture's ability to handle high-speed processing demands with minimal delays. Energy efficiency was another key highlight of the IMC architecture. For neural network inference, the energy consumption decreased from 12.5 joules to 7.2 joules, resulting in a savings of 42.4%. Large-scale data search and sorting operations also saw energy savings exceeding 40%, affirming the architecture's suitability for energy-constrained environments such as edge devices and IoT systems. In terms of throughput, the IMC architecture achieved remarkable gains, with improvements of up to 52% for AI model training. Real-time data processing throughput increased from 800,000 operations per second to 1,210,000 operations per second, reflecting a 51.25% gain, while image classification throughput improved by 48.33%, further demonstrating the architecture's capability to support demanding computational tasks. Overall, the proposed IMC architecture significantly enhances performance by minimizing data movement and leveraging parallelism within memory arrays. These improvements make it a promising solution for applications in AI, machine learning, and real-time analytics, where high performance, energy efficiency, and low latency are critical. Future work will focus on expanding the scalability of the architecture, addressing integration challenges, and exploring hybrid solutions to further optimize performance in broader application domains.

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